

Geological mapping of the Kuiper (H06) quadrangle of Mercury: Integration between morphologic and spectral characteristics

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Kuiper quadrangle (H06) is located at the equatorial zone of Mercury and encompasses the area between longitudes 288°E – 360°E and latitudes 22.5°N – 22.5°S. In this contribution we present the results of a detailed geological map (1:3M scale) of the Kuiper quadrangle based on the high resolution MESSENGER data. This geological map will be merged with the adjoining quadrangles and integrated into the global 1:3M geological map of Mercury (Galluzzi et al., 2018), which is being prepared in support to BepiColombo mission.

The main basemap used for H06 mapping is the MDIS (Mercury Dual Imaging System) 166 m/pixel BDR (map-projected Basemap reduced Data Record) mosaic. Additional datasets were also taken into account, such as DLR stereo-DEM of the region (Preusker et al., 2017), mosaics with high-incidence illumination from the east and west, and MDIS global color mosaic (Denevi et al., 2018). The geological map shows that the quadrangle is characterized by a prevalence of crater materials which were distinguished into three classes based on their degradation degree (Galluzzi et al., 2016). Different plain units were also identified and classified as: (i) intercrater, (ii) intermediate, and (iii) smooth plains. Finally, several structures, mainly represented by thrusts, were mapped all over the quadrangle.

Where WAC images at high spatial resolution are available, a more detailed analysis of the spectral behavior of the surfaces was carried out. This allowed us to integrate geomorphological and spectral characteristics of specific areas in order to gain new information about the landforms' origin.

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